

A NOTE ON RAPID ALKALIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF MAGNESIUM,
PRESENT ALONE OR IN PRESENCE OF CALCIUM, STRONTIUM,
BARIUM AND IN SEA WATER

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Magnesium is estimated using sodium thiosulphate as a reagent after precipitating it as magnesium hydroxide using either sodium hydroxide, baryta water, strontium hydroxide or lime water as a precipitant. Using the last three precipitants, magnesium can be estimated in presence of barium, strontium and calcium respectively. Further, magnesium can be estimated in presence of all the three alkaline earth radicals and in sea water by using lime water as the precipitant.

Magnesium hydroxide reacts with sodium thiosulphate in the cold forming a double salt, $\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2$, disengaging an equivalent amount of alkali which can be titrated. A slight excess of sodium thiosulphate does not interfere with the titration of the alkali. The equation may be represented as

An aliquot part of magnesium chloride solution was taken in a 100 c. c. flask and an excess of carbonate-free lime water was added, which precipitated magnesium hydroxide completely. The mixture of magnesium hydroxide together with the excess alkali was made up to 100 c. c. with distilled water. It was then vigorously shaken for about 10 minutes and filtered through a dry and neutral filter paper (Whatman No. 44), specially prepared for this purpose by washing the original filter paper at least four times and drying. The funnel, the receiver and the pipette used for the subsequent operations were clean and dry.

The filtrate (50 c. c.) was titrated with $N/10$ -HCl, using methyl orange indicator and hence the total excess alkali in 100 c. c. mixture was calculated.

To the remaining filtrate, the filter paper along with the residue was transferred and also the washings of 100 c. c. flask, the funnel and the pipette, used for withdrawing 50 c. c. of the filtrate. Care was taken to carry out all the washings with redistilled water. A carefully neutralised, concentrated solution of sodium thiosulphate was added to the mixture. Sodium thiosulphate reacted with magnesium hydroxide and disengaged an equivalent amount of alkali. The total alkali in the solution was found out by titrating with decinormal hydrochloric acid, using methyl orange indicator.

The excess of the alkali in the mixture being known, the alkali disengaged in the reaction was computed, and hence the amount of magnesium oxide in stock solution calculated. Further, magnesium was estimated in presence of calcium, strontium and barium respectively. The results are shown in Table I. Mean of at least three readings was taken in all the experiments.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	CaO taken.	SrO taken.	BaO taken.	Magnesium oxide		Error	
				taken.	found. g.	Diff.	
1	—	—	—	0.009698 g.	0.009697	-0.001 mg.	-0.01%
2	—	—	—	0.01939	0.01935	-0.04	-0.20
3	0.004 g.	—	—	0.01939	0.01935	-0.04	-0.20
4	0.004	—	—	0.009698	0.009676	-0.022	-0.22
5	0.008	—	—	0.009698	0.009676	-0.022	-0.22
6	0.008	—	—	0.01939	0.01945	+0.06	+0.30
7	0.0016	0.004 g.	0.0016 g.	0.01939	0.01945	+0.06	+0.30
8	0.0024	0.006	0.0024	0.01939	0.01941	+0.02	+0.10
9	0.0016	0.004	0.0016	0.009698	0.009780	+0.82	+0.80
10	0.0024	0.006	0.0024	0.009698	0.009724	+0.026	+0.26

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